

Hope and Hardships of Women Seeking Pregnancy through IVF: A Thematic Analysis

Jyoti Shukla

Department of Psychology, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Infertility is a serious medical issue that accompanies social and psychological challenges, particularly for women. In Indian culture, childbearing is not viewed as a personal choice but a measure of womanhood and failure to this desired social role, which might result in social neglect. Assisted Reproductive Technologies like In Vitro-Fertilization (IVF) provide hope to many couples struggling with Infertility but has significant stigma attached to it. Women undergoing IVF treatment has to face several unique emotional, psychological, social and financial challenges which needs to be addressed. This research paper is an attempt to explore lived experiences of women undergoing IVF treatment in India. A semi-structured interview schedule was used to probe emotional experiences, social stigma faced and coping strategies of 27 women (aged 32-45) seeking pregnancy through IVF in Lucknow, India. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2019) was done to analyze data using mixed method deductive inductive coding approach. The analysis revealed two meta-themes: Hope and Hardships. The subthemes under Hope are 'Perseverance', which shows internal motivation, optimistic attitude participants hold despite treatment failures, and 'Social Pillars', which indicates participants' perception about emotional and moral support from spouse, family and hospital staff. Sub-themes under Hardships include 'Why Me' showing psychological distress, Incomplete woman captures social stigma, Silent Struggle presents isolation and Juggling Roles indicates practical burdens related to infertility and IVF treatment. The results of this study highlight two extremes showing resilience and vulnerability in lived experiences of women seeking pregnancy through IVF treatment. The results also stress the need to integrate psychosocial support during fertility treatments.

Keywords: Infertility, IVF, thematic analysis, mental health, psychological support

Infertility has become a global health issue in today's time; it affects approximately 17.5% of the adult population, which simply means one in every sixth person is facing this concern (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023). Infertility can be medically defined as the inability to achieve pregnancy after one-year of unprotected sexual contact. In India, the prevalence of infertility is between 2.5% and 14%, some regional-specific prevalence is as high as 16.8% for primary infertility (Ganguly & Unisa, 2010; Widge, 2005). Despite being a medical diagnosis, infertility has much deeper social, cultural and gender specific importance in India. India is a family-oriented cultural society where motherhood is not only a woman's personal achievement but also a social role, a yardstick to measure her womanhood (Bhardwaj, 2016; Hasanpoor-Azghdy et al., 2015). The failure to achieve this desired social role led to stigma, social exclusion and unhappy marital and familial relationships, particularly for women (Kucuk & Koruk, 2022; Roberts et al., 2020).

Assisted Reproductive Technologies (ART), especially in-vitro fertilization (IVF), have been providing hope to many couples but the journey through IVF is like an emotional roller-coaster ride. The treatment cycle is very physically exhausting, due to hormonal injections, frequent appointments, and invasive procedures. IVF

treatment in India is very financially draining due to extremely expensive medical services with minimal insurance coverage (Boivin et al., 2007; Widge, 2005). The stress of waiting for a positive treatment outcome after multiple cycles adds to this, by triggering anxiety, depression and burnout (Holter et al., 2021; Malina et al., 2016). The expectation of a successful pregnancy after multiple failed attempts make this journey very emotionally challenging and physically painful (Boivin & Takefman, 1995).

In the Indian context, the psychological stress of IVF treatment procedure is multiplied due to societal pressure of becoming a mother and proving one's worth. Despite numerous studies proving that male counterparts are equally responsible for inability to conceive, women partners are blamed for it without any doubt by society (Greil, 1997; Kundu et al., 2022). Rural and uneducated women even internalize this blame and feel guilty for not fulfilling the expectations of society. Most women even conceal their husband's infertility to protect the family's 'so-called prestige' in the social circle. Thus, facing an invisible burden of personal suffering and social neglect (Ganguly & Unisa, 2010; Jejeebhoy, 2004). A personal medical issue is turned into a stigmatized social crisis by labelling these women as "baanjh" (sterile). The social stigma of infertility leads to social exclusion from religious and family rituals, highlighting the intensity of cultural importance of bearing a child for a woman (Roberts et al., 2020; Bhardwaj, 2016).

However, after all these psychological pressures, women also draw enormous reservoirs of hope and resilience. Prayers, rituals, temple visits, and even the spiritual adoption of deities are forms of religious coping that are common and deeply rooted in culture (Jisha & Thomas, 2016). The huge psychological effect may be reduced with the psychological support from partners, family members, and peers receiving similar therapies (Ni et al., 2021; Dancet et al.,

Author Note

Jyoti Shukla, Senior Research Fellow, Department of Psychology University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Jyoti Shukla, Senior Research Fellow, Department of Psychology University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
E-mail: 123.jyotishukla@gmail.com

2011). Many women show resilience even during times of discouragement, emphasizing the twofold role of hope as a coping strategy and a source of strength (Cousineau & Domar, 2007). Positive thinking is a necessary trait during IVF treatment, as it enhances the perseverance of the woman but also deepens the pain after every failed attempt.

Despite the magnitude of these challenges, psychosocial support is under-addressed in the fertility care ecosystem of India. Even though the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Act, 2021 requires pre and post treatment counseling, there are inefficiencies at the implementation level and many women reported having limited, if any, access to psychological treatment (Hassan et al., 2022; Gazette of India, 2021). Studies suggest that women experiencing infertility treatments face similar psychological distress as people who are diagnosed with chronic and life-threatening diseases like cancer or HIV (Greil, 1997; Holka-Pokorska et al., 2015). As formal mental health support is still rare, and psychological counseling is stigmatized by culture, the help-seeking behaviors are more inhibited (Kucuk & Koruk, 2022; Ganguly & Unisa, 2010).

In this context, there is a critical need to understand the lived experience of women undergoing IVF, not just as recipients of medical intervention, but as persons facing a complex socio-emotional issue made complicated by stigma surrounding infertility. Most popular quantitative researches, which is based on clinical contexts in Western environments, has rarely succeeded in understanding the multi-layered meanings of infertility in the lives of Indian women (Widge, 2005; Dancet et al., 2011). Therefore, this study takes the qualitative phenomenological approach of investigating the lived experiences of Indian women during the IVF process. It seeks to understand the emotional textures of infertility from self-blame, shame, and silence to endurance and spiritual strength. These insights will help in forming more culturally sensitive, emotionally supportive, and patient-centered fertility care in India.

Research Questions

This research, which is guided by the previous literature probes comprehensive and open-ended research questions that highlight the emotional stress, social stigma, and everyday struggles of Indian women undergoing IVF treatment. The research questions are:

- Which internal and external sources help women overcome challenges of IVF treatment?
- Which emotional, personal and social struggles are faced by women during the IVF treatment?
- How does internal and external sources assist women overcome or cope with the struggles during their IVF treatment?

Method

Participants

Twenty-seven women (aged between 32 - 45 years, mean = 38 years) undergoing in vitro fertilization (IVF) treatment in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India were included in the study. Participants were recruited by a purposive sampling method. Data collection took place until the dataset represented a broad array of perspectives, and no new themes were emerging, which indicated qualitative saturation. At the time of the data collection, all the participants were in the controlled ovarian stimulation (COS) phase of IVF treatment. This phase is

characterized by the administration of hormonal injections every day to develop multiple eggs that need frequent visits to the clinic for ultrasound and hormonal tests. The COS phase is said to be one of the most physically and emotionally tiring phases of IVF because of heavy medications, bodily discomfort, side effects of medications, and the pressure of emotions of having a successful outcome. In terms of the medical history, 17 participants were starting their first IVF cycle, while six women had previous unsuccessful attempts at IVF. The other four women had gone through other unsuccessful fertility treatments such as intrauterine insemination (IUI). The majority of the participants were highly educated as 23 women had postgraduate degrees and others were graduates. In terms of profession, nine women were working as teachers or bank employees, two of them ran small businesses, and the rest were homemakers.

Only women going through IVF treatment were included in the study. All study participants were able to communicate in either Hindi or English, provided informed consent and agreed to participate in a face-to-face interview. A detailed summary of demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants is provided in Table 1.

Table 1

Participant Demographic Characteristics (N = 27)

Characteristic	n	%
Age (years)		
32-35	6	22.22
36-39	12	44.44
40-45	9	33.33
Duration of Marriage		
More than 5 years	27	100.00
Fertility Treatment History		
First IVF cycle	17	62.96
Two or more IVF failures	6	22.22
Previous IUI failures	4	14.81
Occupation		
Employed (teachers, bank staff)	9	33.33
Businesswomen	2	7.41
Homemakers	16	59.26
Education		
Postgraduate	23	85.19
Graduate	4	14.81

Procedure

The data was gathered through individual, face-to-face semi-structured interviews carried out from November 2024 through April 2025. The interview guide included five open-ended questions that sought to cover the objectives of the research. The schedule was developed on the basis of a comprehensive literature review and was reviewed by three experts in the fields of psychology and reproductive health. Some minor changes were made on the basis of feedback. A pilot interview followed in order to check the practicality and relevance of the questions. The questions in these interviews covered participants' fertility experiences and IVF journey; emotional experiences of the IVF procedure; support from spouse, siblings, and extended relatives; difficulties like financial stress and physical discomfort; sources of resilience and personal strategies. These had been recorded by consent on audio and transcribed on that basis.

Data Analysis

The transcripts obtained from the interviews were thematically analyzed, following the steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006, 2019). The initial point was feeding the data into NVivo15 software, which helps in the organization and thematic coding of the data from the interviews. The first step proceeds with the repetitive reading of the interview transcripts in order to gain a profound understanding of the data. Following this, the initial coding was done through the line-by-line coding method, involving the highlighting of prominent information related to the research aims. The thematic analysis considered a combination approach, of both deductive coding, where the coding followed the guidelines outlined in the previously designed semi-structured interview schedule, and inductive coding, involving the development of ideas based on the narratives. Finally, the thematic analysis entailed the structuring of the related thematic codes into more general ones, based upon the general meaning. This finally led to the development of two meta-themes, capturing the experiences encountered by the women receiving the IVF procedure.

For adding authenticity as well as validity to the findings, the member checking technique has also been applied. The findings,

interpretations, and conclusions obtained from the study have been mailed to the participants. This action has helped in getting feedback from a total of 18 out of the 27 participants, who validated the findings and made minor corrections. There has been no new information revealed during this stage. This technique recommended by Birt et al. (2016) has ensured the validity of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

All participants provided written informed consent before interviews. They were given detailed information on the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights (including the right to refuse or withdraw at any time). Confidentiality was strictly maintained: no personal identifiers were recorded in transcripts, and data were stored in password-protected files accessible only to the research team. Pseudonyms or ID codes were used in place of names to ensure privacy. Throughout the study, we followed ethical guidelines for human research, safeguarding participants' welfare and autonomy at all stages.

Results

Table 2

Themes, Descriptions, and Illustrative Verbatims from Interviews with Women Undergoing IVF Treatment

Meta-Theme	Theme	Description	Illustrative Verbatims
Hope	Perseverance	Persistent belief in the possibility of a successful outcome despite repeated failures and emotional exhaustion.	<i>"I talk to myself every time that this time, everything will be good. I have to believe it will happen one day."</i> <i>"No matter how bad it gets, a small part of me still believes there's a chance."</i>
	Social Pillars	Emotional, moral, and practical support from husbands, family members, and healthcare providers that sustained women's emotional resilience through their IVF journey.	<i>"Whenever I break down, my husband holds me and says we'll get through this together."</i> <i>"My mother keeps telling me, don't lose heart, we're with you."</i> <i>"The doctor's kind words made me feel less alone."</i>
Hardships	Why Me	The emotional turbulence of stress, anxiety, helplessness, and questioning fate following repeated failures, leading to feelings of being singled out by misfortune.	<i>"Every time I take a pregnancy test, I close my eyes and pray for good news. But when it's negative again, I feel like fate is never on my side."</i> <i>"Sometimes I ask myself, why is this happening only to me?"</i>
	Incomplete Woman	Feelings of shame, guilt, embarrassment, and inadequacy due to infertility, with fear of being perceived as incomplete by society, family, and oneself.	<i>"I feel like I've failed as a woman. What's the point if I can't give my family what they want?"</i> <i>"I'm embarrassed to talk about it. It makes me feel like I'm less than other women."</i>
	Silent Struggle	Secrecy, concealment, and emotional isolation in managing infertility are driven by fear of social judgment, pity, or unsolicited advice.	<i>"It's something you just can't tell everyone. People don't understand. They start treating you differently."</i> <i>"At work, I make excuses for my leaves. I don't want anyone to know what I'm going through."</i>
	Juggling Roles	The challenge of managing multiple personal, social, and occupational responsibilities alongside IVF treatment demands is compounded by financial burden and social expectations.	<i>"When my appointments are on weekdays, I have to request leave and make up reasons. I worry what my boss will think if he finds out."</i> <i>"Even though I don't work outside, I feel pressure at home. Relatives keep asking when we'll have good news."</i> <i>"This treatment drains not just your body, but your savings too."</i>

Findings from the qualitative study examining the experiences of the women undergoing IVF treatment are presented in this section. The findings are structured in a way to specifically address the three

questions being sought in the study.

The two meta-themes identified from the qualitative study are Hope and Hardships. These two meta-themes represent the duality

between resilience and the difficulties experienced by the subjects in the study. The two meta-themes consist of various themes identified from patterns in the narratives provided by the subjects.

Meta-Theme: Hope

“Hope is not only the expectation of a positive outcome, but an active belief that one can find a way to strive and gain the motivation to attain valued goals despite obstacles” (Snyder, 2002).

Despite the challenges involved in their fertility experiences, participants actively described their experiences of emotional resilience and optimism to persevere in a cycle of uncertainty and disappointment. The meta-theme of emotional strength and optimism included two sub-themes: Perseverance and Social Pillars.

Answering the first research question, 'What internal and external sources do women use to cope with the challenges of undergoing IVF treatment?', two main sources of coping with the challenges of IVF treatment have been identified in the narratives: these are personal psychological resources and external relationship resources. These have been subsumed under the meta theme of Hope: Perseverance and Social Pillars.

Perseverance

They showed evidence of a personal conviction that success was possible despite failed attempts. This was often a function of faith and personal strength and their need to keep their optimism alive. Few participants described their experience as such:

“I am convinced that if I follow the doctor's advice properly, it will happen one day [P23, P4].”

Despite the emotional burden, several of the women reported hopes of positive results:

“Even after two unsuccessful attempts, a significant part of me believes there's a definite chance [P6, P17, P20, P24].”

This optimistic outlook, no matter how internally maintained, became an important psychological tool in dealing with the uncertain nature of IVF.

Social Pillars

In addition to personal resourcefulness, the importance of supportive relationships was emphasized as a key resource that helped keep the emotional well-being of the participants healthy and strong. The social support sources for the participants comprised spouses, parents, parental spouses, and healthcare workers, who all encouraged and helped the women stay hopeful and emotionally sound, as is evident from the following:

“Whenever I have a breakdown, my husband is there to hug me and reassure me that we'll get through things together.” [P1, P3, P5, P16.]”

Others participants shared similar experiences when they got quiet but dependable reassurance from family members and medical staff:

“My mother-in-law doesn't know much about this treatment, but still she keeps telling me not lose hope, and they are with me' [P14, P2].”

“My doctor is supportive that makes me feel less alone [P27, P7].”

These were important, not always overt, sources of support, and these sources were crucial in allowing these women to survive treatment and the social pressures that surrounded it.

Meta-Theme: Hardships

The second research question, 'What emotional, personal, and social

struggles women experience throughout their IVF treatment?', is explored through the meta-theme of Hardships that comprised four core themes: Why Me, Incomplete Woman, Silent Struggle, and Juggling Roles. These themes capture the extent of emotional and social suffering experienced by women undergoing IVF.

Why Me

This theme symbolizes the emotional turmoil that the participants experienced, such as stress, anxiety, hopelessness, and reasons to question fate. The series of failed experiences emotionally drained the women and made them feel that they alone were the victims of bad luck.

“Every time I take a pregnancy test, I close my eyes and pray for good results. But when it turns out to be negative again, I always have the feeling that I am never on the right side of fate.” [P2, P20, P24]

“Sometimes, I ask myself questions like, 'Why is all this happening to me alone? What is wrong with me that all these things are happening to me?' [P21, P27, P3, P6]”

In these reflections, the pain and hopelessness had come through very strongly.

Incomplete Woman

This theme captures the emotions of shame, guilt, and inadequacy that women experienced as a consequence of their infertility. The women were afraid of being viewed as incomplete by their families, communities, and even themselves because motherhood was linked to their identity.

“I feel like I've failed as a woman. What's the point if I can't give my family a child [P9, P24]”

“I'm embarrassed to talk about it. It makes me feel like I'm less than other women. [P6, P15, P21].”

“Somewhere, I feel guilty towards my in-laws. They didn't deserve this.” [P2, P17]

Such feelings of being viewed in this way further contributed to the feelings of social inferiority, guilt, and emotional distance.

Silent Struggle

Participants often spoke about hiding their IVF journey from friends, family, and even colleagues to avoid being judged, pitied, or advised. This secrecy led to feelings of loneliness.

“It's something you just can't tell everyone. People don't understand, they start treating you differently [P4, P12, P18, P24].”

“At work, I make excuses for my leaves. I don't want anyone to know what I'm going through in my personal life [P8, P13, P19, P21].”

“Even in family gatherings, I avoid this topic. It's easier to keep quiet [P2, P3, P25].”

This silence was another factor that contributed to the pain of infertility.

Juggling Roles

This theme is an expression of the challenges that the participants undergo in managing fertility treatment and their roles. Working women as well as homemakers faced similar challenges in managing their roles while coping with the physical and emotional stress of IVF.

“Pressure from work and my fertility journey together is very difficult for me [P7, P13, P20, P26].”

“Because of the heavy medications, I feel physically and mentally drained. So, I avoid going to any family gatherings [P4, P10, P20, P22].”

In addition, the cost of undergoing several IVF procedures was identified as a challenge:

“This treatment is draining not only your body but also your finances. Eventually, it will feel like you are risking everything—money, time, health, and sanity—just for a baby [P5, P9, P11, P16].”

This financial load further contributed to the complexity of role management, as well as the emotional distress of the participants.

'Hope' as an armor against 'Hardships':

Finally, the third research question, 'How do these internal and external sources help women overcome or manage these struggles while undergoing IVF treatment?', is answered by the combination of both meta-themes. The presence of internal sources such as Perseverance and external sources such as Social Pillars enabled the women to cope with the emotional pain apparent in the themes of Hardships.

For example, one of the participants who was affected by the societal influence said:

“Sometimes it gets really overwhelming, but just talking to my husband makes me feel calm again.” [P10]

This means that coping was not a trait but a process that was affected by emotional challenges and relational buffers.

Discussion

This qualitative study examined the experiences of women undergoing IVF, and two meta-themes emerged: Hope and Hardships. These themes are representative of the emotional, social, and cultural nuances of infertility, as has been found in Indian and International Qualitative Research (Volgsten et al., 2010; Dancet et al., 2014; Patel et al., 2018). The results of this study underscore the fact that IVF is not only a physically demanding procedure but is also situated within the cultural construct of womanhood and motherhood.

Hope: Perseverance and Social Pillars

The participants in this study emphasized the importance of perseverance in pursuing IVF. This is because hope can be considered a powerful tool in coping with adversity. For the participants in this study, hope was seen as a form of perseverance in the face of adversity. Similarly, Ni et al. (2021) showed that social support and good relationships with partners are positively associated with hope in women undergoing IVF procedures. In this study, spouses and immediate family members played an important role in encouraging these women. The accounts showed that spouses were supportive and encouraged these women during treatment. In Ghana, Anaman-Torgbor et al. (2021) also found that spouses and medical professionals offered social, emotional, and even financial support to women, which kept them positive throughout the fertility journey. Volgsten et al. (2010) also found in Sweden that most men took up a protective and supportive role to help their wives cope with infertility. Therefore, women's hope was made possible by the presence of strong social supports (loving partners, supportive family, & caring professionals), which kept hope alive. As Ni et al. (2021) concluded, “establishing a good social support and relationship network could effectively improve women's hope levels

during IVF.”

Hardships (Why Me, Incomplete Woman, Silent Struggle, Juggling Roles)

Alongside hope, women have shown strong emotional hardships. Many women showed shock, anger, and hurt, often asking, “Why me?” about infertility. Feelings of self-blame and injustice were shown in statements such as “everybody believes it is my fault for not conceiving.” These feelings are in line with previous studies. Volgsten et al. (2010) found that women feel unresolved grief and guilt after unsuccessful IVF, feeling frustrated and angry with their situation. Under the theme “Incomplete Woman,” a sense of identity crisis was expressed. The inability to conceive made these women feel as if they were failing at womanhood. In one study, it was found that “the inability to become pregnant makes them feel as if they are less than others. That is because they cannot get pregnant... [they] are lower than others.’ The belief that motherhood is at the foundation of a woman's very identity has been expressed in other cultures as well.” The impact of infertility can be such that it interferes with one's objectives and identity in life and can even induce a sense of loss as if one's identity has been diminished because one could not create life.

The Silent Struggle theme addressed how the problem was dealt with in secret. The subjects have concealed their pain from other people, struggling in secret. In this regard, one of the subjects stated, “I don't like anybody to know anything about my infertility issues, so I hide it.” They choose to cover their pain at work or being busy to avoid being pitied. Kucuk and Koruk (2022) found that many women had hidden issues with their fertility (infertility behind a mask), as they did not wish to be stigmatized. This suffering of the IVF journey mirrors the loneliness of the IVF experience: “a woman experiences the threat of rumor, tactless remarks, and sympathies ('you are wasting your time') without visible consternation.” This silent suffering corresponds with the findings made in the study conducted by Holter et al. in 2021, stating that IVF failure can result in significant emotional distress, and women need early counseling intervention post failed cycle.

Finally, in regard to the theme of “Juggling Roles,” there are real pressures that are illustrated by the sheer number of women who related their exhaustion at juggling their appointments for their IVF cycles with their other roles. Many talked of cost in addition to their stress: the participants to be 'anxious, stressed-up, exhausted, and financially burdened with ART treatments'. The pressures of being stretched too thin are in line with previous findings: “IVF is a trial on one's physical, emotional, and financial health” (Cousineau & Domar, 2007). Coping mechanisms were by rescheduling or postponing one's needs, although “Juggling” was an added stress factor. The themes of hardship provide understanding about how infertility not only challenges one's biological system but also one's social resources, as women in these circumstances are forced to second-guess themselves while trying to live a normal life, while hiding their grief.

In conclusion, the stories of the women interviewed portray a contradictory experience of hope sustained through perseverance and support networks, as well as painful experiences of blame, shame, and stress. In general, the narratives emphasized that IVF is more than a biomedical procedure and involves a personal experience of hope and suffering. It corroborates other research carried out globally on infertility among women, emphasizing that

IVF is more than a procreative procedure and encompasses painful and hopeful experiences. The study supports the idea that, in IVF practices, psychosocial support is essential and that the resistance and support structures of patients ought to be encouraged, as well as the feeling of inadequacy or grief (Cousineau & Domar, 2007; Dancet et al., 2011). Future research efforts can aim towards counseling and support for the woman to “carry hopes” while “bearing hardships” of the IVF experience.

Implications of the Study

There are critical implications that lie within the conclusion drawn from the results achieved in this study for psychological care, reproductive health care, and social support in relation to the following: Mental health care programs need to be developed in collaboration with IVF centers, Counseling and Psychological Support needs to be carried out periodically for the intended purpose of dealing with anxiety, grief, and role-related stress for female companions, Family-inclusive and culture-based models need to be fostered because there is conclusive proof that rests on the core point that 'the major influence of the family and partners is most evident for the lasting upkeep of female companions in relation to general factors concerning their emotional well-being.' Mental health professionals require necessary training for the intended purpose to understand that there is exclusive psychosocial circularity associated with 'individual infertility in general within Indian society.' Group counseling programs need to be efficiently implemented in collaboration with a 'mix and match of individual and group support,' since these programs will enable female companions to gain access to communication. There will be an opportunity for emotional ventilation and validation, as well as learning to adapt to strategies for dealing with the situation. Narrative therapy, emotional expression techniques, and hope-focused counseling will be very valuable in this regard. Finally, public awareness and policy support are necessary to demystify and establish psychological support as an integral part of infertility treatment. This will enable women to journey through their treatment processes emotionally strong and dignified.

References

- Anaman-Torgbor, J. A., Jonathan, J. W. A., Asare, L., Osarfo, B., Attivor, R., Bonsu, A., & Tarkang, E. E. (2021). Experiences of women undergoing assisted reproductive technology in Ghana: A qualitative analysis of their experiences. *PLOS ONE*, *16*(8), e0255957.
- Anaman-Torgbor, J., Adu-Appiah, E., Ampofo, E. A., & Boamah Mensah, A. (2021). Psychological impact and coping strategies among women undergoing in-vitro fertilization treatment in Ghana. *BMC Women's Health*, *21*(1), 364. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-015335>
- Bhardwaj, A. (2016). *Conceptions: Infertility and procreative technologies in India*. Orient Blackswan.
- Boivin, J., & Takefman, J. E. (1996). Stress and distress in in-vitro fertilization. *Human Reproduction*, *10*(12), 3225-3232. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.humrep.a135906>
- Boivin, J., Bunting, L., Collins, J. A., & Nygren, K. G. (2007). International estimates of infertility prevalence and treatment-seeking: Potential need and demand for infertility medical care. *Human Reproduction*, *22*(6), 1506-1512. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dem046>
- Cousineau, T. M., & Domar, A. D. (2007). Psychological impact of infertility. *Best Practice and Research Clinical Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, *21*(2), 293-308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2006.12.003>
- Dancet, E. A. F., D'Hooghe, T. M., Spiessens, C., de Sutter, P., & Nelen, W. (2011). Quality indicators for all dimensions of patient-centered infertility care: A consensus approach. *Human Reproduction*, *26*(4), 827-833. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deq359>
- Ganguly, E., & Unisa, S. (2010). Infertility in India: Levels, patterns and consequences. *Population and Development Review*, *36*(2), 208-229.
- Greil, A. L. (1997). Infertility and psychological distress: A critical review of the literature. *Social Science and Medicine*, *45*(11), 1679-1704. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(97\)00102-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(97)00102-0)
- Hasanpoor-Azghdy, S. B., Simbar, M., & Vedadhir, A. (2015). The social consequences of infertility among Iranian women: A qualitative study. *International Journal of Reproductive BioMedicine*, *13*(10), 665-676.
- Hassan, A., Singh, R., & Mukhra, R. (2022). Quality of infertility care services and emotional health of South Asian women: A mixed-methods study. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, *15*, 1131-1146. <https://doi.org/10.2147/P.RBM.S359228>
- Holter, H., Bergh, C., & Gejervall, A.L. (2021). Lost and lonely: A qualitative study of women's experiences of no embryo transfer owing to non-fertilization or poor embryo quality. *Human Reproduction Open*, *2021*(4), hoab045.
- Holter, H., Sandin-Boj6, A. K., Gejervall, A. L., Wikland, M., Wilde Larsson, B., & Bergh, C. (2021). Quality of care in an IVF programme from the patient's perspective: Development of a validated instrument. *Human Reproduction Open*, *2021*(1), hoab011. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hropen/hoab011>
- Kucuk, M. G., & Koruk, I. (2022). Perceived stigma, coping strategies, and psychological distress in infertile women: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Reproductive and Infant Psychology*, *40*(3), 296-308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/002646838.2021.1963267>
- Kucuk, S., & Koruk, F. (2022). Being an infertile woman in a highly fertile region of Turkey: Stigmatisation and coping experiences. *Electronic Journal of General Medicine*, *19*(2), em346.
- Kundu, S., Ali, M., & Dhillon, P. (2022). Understanding the socio-cultural dynamics of infertility: Insights from women undergoing in-vitro fertilization in Haryana. *Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Ethics*, *2*(1), 1-15.
- Newton, C. R., Hearn, M. T., & Yuzpe, A. A. (1990). Psychological assessment and follow-up after in vitro fertilization: Assessing the impact of failure. *Fertility and Sterility*, *54*(5), 879-886.
- Ni, M., Li, H., & Xu, H. (2021). Marital adjustment and hope among Chinese women undergoing repeated IVF: The mediating role of perceived social support. *BMC Women's Health*, *21*, 227. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-01379-x>
- Ni, Y., Huang, L., Tong, C., Qian, W., & Fang, Q. (2021). Analysis of the levels of hope and influencing factors in infertile women with first-time and repeated IVF-ET cycles. *Reproductive Health*, *18*, 200.
- Papadatou, D., Papaligoura, Z. G., & Bellali, T. (2016). From Infertility to Successful Third-Party Reproduction: The Trajectory of Greek Women. *Qualitative health research*, *26*(3), 399-410. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732314566322>
- Peters, K. (2003). In pursuit of motherhood: The IVF experience. *Contemporary Nurse*, *14*(3), 258-270. <https://doi.org/10.5172/conu.14.3.258>
- Ranjbar, F., Behboodi-Moghadam, Z., Borimnejad, L., Ghaffari, S.R., & Akhondi, M.M. (2015). Experiences of Infertile Women Seeking Assisted Pregnancy in Iran: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Reproduction and Infertility*, *16*, 221 - 228.
- Roberts, E., Grubb, C., & Bhaktal, N. (2020). Women and infertility in a pronatalist culture: Mental health in the slums of Mumbai. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(22), 8565. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228565>
- Vander Borgh, M., & Wyns, C. (2018). Fertility and infertility: Definition and epidemiology. *Clinical Biochemistry*, *62*, 2-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2018.03.012>
- Volgsten, H., Svanberg, A. S., & Olsson, P. (2010). Unresolved grief in women and men in Sweden three years after undergoing unsuccessful in vitro fertilization treatment. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*, *89*, 1290-1297.
- Widge A. (2005). Seeking conception: experiences of urban Indian women with in vitro fertilisation. *Patient Education and Counseling*, *59*(3), 226-233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2005.07.014>
- World Health Organization (2023). *Infertility affects 1 in 6 people globally*. <https://www.who.int/news/item/04-04-2023-1-in-6-people-globally-affected-by-infertility-who>
- Ying, X., Zhou, Y., Jin, Y., Wu, D., Kong, L., Dong, P., Ji, X., Cheng, X., & Zhang, L. (2024). An insurmountable obstacle: Experiences of Chinese women undergoing in vitro fertilization. *PLoS ONE*, *19*(10), e0311660. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311660>

Received January 14, 2025

Revision received January 27, 2025

Accepted January 29, 2025